

Global and regional level of use of buildings and roads prepared by AI for OSM mapping

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OpenStreetMap (hereinafter OSM) is created by volunteer mappers, either individuals or organized groups. Most of them map individually, and some of them during organized mapping parties at so-called mapathons. The motivation of these volunteers is altruism and the effort to be beneficial to the community [1].

However, despite their great efforts, many world areas are still insufficiently mapped. In 2020, regions with low and medium human development accounted for 28% of the buildings and 16% of the roads mapped in OSM, although they were home to 46% of the global population [2]. Using AI-assisted tools was seen as one possibility to fill data gaps. The main aim of our study is to research the actual level of AI-assisted mapping in OSM. We show the overall global level and highlight differences between countries.

The most developed projects using AI objects for OSM mapping are the Rapid editor and mapwith.ai plugin for the JOSM editor. These tools allow mappers to use prepared AI buildings generated by Microsoft [3] and Google in cooperation with ESRI [4, 5] and prepared AI roads generated by Meta [6]. Microsoft organized mapping in Kenya and Nigeria using their global AI dataset of buildings [7]. Meta similarly uses their global AI dataset of roads for mapping in Thailand, Indonesia, Malaysia, India, Tanzania, and Vietnam [8]. The Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team is working on a fAIr project that could produce local models generating AI data for specific regions [9].

During the crisis after the Turkey-Syria Earthquake in 2023, these technologies played a pivotal role in disaster response, illustrating the potential for AI in supporting humanitarian mapping [10]. However, the OSM community's reactions to the results of the AI-assisted mapping campaign were often mixed [10, 11].

The main research question of our study was, "What are the differences between AI-assisted mapping and traditional mapping concerning editing behavior?" The question deals with the editing pattern of AI and non-AI data. There are concerns within the OSM community that AI-assisted mapping will lead to less community engagement and could undermine the contributor base of OSM in the long run. OSM community attitudes toward

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imports and automated edits can be negative and cautious [12]. Human mappers can be mistrustful of the result of AI algorithms that often remain in a black box for them [13], or they can even feel that they are being replaced by AI algorithms for OSM mapping.

We used an extract of all contributions made to OSM during 2021-2023 derived from a combination of the OSHDB developed by the Heidelberg Institute for Geoinformation Technology (hereinafter HeiGIT) and the OSM changeset database. There are three types of operations with objects in OSM: creating, editing (=modifying), and deleting. We focused on creating and editing and searched for differences between buildings and roads mapped using AI and buildings and roads in general.

Buildings were defined for our study as objects with any value in tag *building=**. Buildings mapped with the use of AI-assisted tools (hereinafter AI buildings) are subset from buildings identified by element tag source with values "*microsoft/BuildingFootprints*" (prepared by Microsoft) and "*esri/Google_Africa_Buildings*" (prepared by Google and ESRI).

Only the most important types of roads were used in our study to analyze the roads because they form the transportation network's backbone. They are identified by the following values of tag *highway*: *motorway*, *motorway_link*, *trunk*, *primary*, *primary_link*, *secondary*, *secondary_link*, *tertiary*, *tertiary_link*, *unclassified*, *residential* [14]. Roads mapped using AI-assisted tools (hereinafter AI roads) are subset from roads identified by the following values in changeset tag hashtags: *#nsroadimport*, *#mapwithai*, *#MapWithAI*. Also, the value "*RapiD*" in the *element* tags can identify the AI road.

The numbers of created and edited AI buildings in 2021-2023 were extracted to analyze the buildings. They were divided by the number of all created and all edited buildings. Lengths of created and edited AI roads in 2021-2023 were extracted to analyze the roads. They were divided by the total lengths of created and edited roads.

The relative share of AI buildings from all newly created buildings was 5.2% in 2021, 12% in 2022, and 14.8% in June 2023. The relative share of AI buildings from all edited buildings was 0.7% in 2021, 3.2% in 2022, and 4.2% in June 2023.

The relative share of AI roads from all newly created important roads was 14.7% in 2021, 15.1% in 2022, and 7.7% in June 2023. The relative share of AI roads from all edited important roads was 8.3% in 2021, 5.7% in 2022, and 3.1% in June 2023.

The results show that the global level of using AI buildings and AI roads for creating new buildings and roads is always under 20%. It is increasing year to year in the case of buildings, but not in the case of roads. Portion of AI buildings and AI roads is higher in the case of creating new objects than in the case of editing existing objects. It means that AI buildings and AI roads are (after their creation) only rarely actualized.

We also searched for differences in using AI-assisted mapping between countries. We wanted to know the absolute numbers of AI buildings and the relative portion of AI buildings on all buildings in every country. We used ohsome API developed by HeiGIT to reach the results, allowing access to the entire OSM history. This analysis was prepared only for buildings because ohsome API allows to search only element tags, not changeset tags, so identification of AI roads was not possible.

The result is in Figure 1. The highest absolute and relative numbers of AI buildings can be found in the USA, Turkey, and Kenya. A high absolute number is also in Nigeria. High relative numbers are also found in Morocco, Venezuela, and Australia, but the absolute numbers of AI buildings are low.

This result shows that the higher relative share of AI buildings and roads exists almost only in countries where Microsoft coordinates mapping using AI datasets they created (USA, Kenya, Nigeria) or where a special humanitarian mapping project using AI-assisted tools was held by The Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (Turkey).

Figure 1. Numbers of AI buildings and portion (in %) of AI buildings on all buildings.

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